

INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL

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ABSTRACT

the article examines the relevance of human capital development and effective use of labor capacity

Mankind has stepped into a new stage of development - the information community on the basis of the production process, the promotion and use of information, at the same time, the talk is not only about information, but also about information that is first of all about knowledge, that is, information about the laws of nature and society, about the skills and abilities of people, Instead of an industrial economy dominated by mass production, a cognitive economy has come, bunda creative ,ualual labor plays an important role, while the labor force - as Capital-acquires human capital.

In a knowledge-based economy, the role of man in the creation of common wealth increases in the existing way. He was at a

certain level higher than other production factors. Man has become not only a subject of reproductive labor with creative elements, but also often, a subject of creative labor, which has a wide range of diverse needs, not only developing abilities, high professionalism.

Education is an asset of human capital. Today, this asset is becoming a decisive factor of the country's scientific and technical potential and market success. The priority in the competition is determined not by the scale of the country, the rich natural resources, the power of financial capital, but by the level of education and the volume of accumulated general knowledge.

Through the development of human capital and the improvement of post-Oyo

and post-Oyo vocational education as its central link, the CIS republics, as well as Uzbekistan, where the human and labor potential is currently being quietly used, create opportunities to overcome economic recession. Therefore, the study of the problems of increasing labor efficiency and the use of human capital is now considered not only topical, but in general is promoted in the first place in the structure of socio-economic research. Particular attention should be paid to the economic aspects of education, since the effective use of the accumulated World Scientific and educational potential has become the main condition for sustainable economic and social development of society.

The evaluation of the value of human capital and the analysis of the existing approaches to the effectiveness of investment in human capital showed different approaches that can be divided into two main groups: cost-effective and profitable. The cost-effective approach is usually based on the addition of the sum of the costs and other costs of the society to the training, professional training of specialists, which are then invested in human capital. The principle of profitability implies an assessment of the income of workers, reflecting the proceeds from the funds included in the level of education and qualifications in accordance with.

TECHNIQUES.

In the concept of the system of indicators, which is widely distributed in the West, it is proposed to add only highly qualified personnel to the group of "employees", in which the general indicator K_{kue} (coefficient of capital participation) characterizes the coefficient of human

capital participation in the creation of additional value:

$$K_{kue} = \frac{\text{skilled laborers} + \text{advantage} + \text{depreciation}}{\text{skilled workers and staff} + \text{contributors (owners)}}$$

It is through this that the increase in the importance of human capital removes the difference between highly qualified employees and entrepreneurs (shareholders (owners)), because their goal is to develop one - value-added. Although, if there is a dependence between unskilled employees, owners of production, qualified employees and entrepreneurs, then in quantitative terms, the first two groups are highly skilled workers and employees, as well as entrepreneurs, who gradually lose their place. This increase in the importance of human capital consists in the enrichment of capital-property and the attainment of capital - functions.

Despite the fact that the yieldadorlik of investment in human capital is excessive, there are no absolute flawless criteria. It is necessary to study the concrete conditions in each specific situation, to determine only the best investment criterion, in which the system of interrelated criteria is successfully applied.

The models that have been developed to this day provide for the level, and not the quality of Education. The level of education on the one hand affects the qualification of the employee, his professional skills, achievements, ability to creative work. On the other hand, higher education is a higher qualification and does not always guarantee a higher income to a person. Finally, there is no clear motivation and high level of education that is not directed towards result and high qualification, effective activities and high income.

Thus, no matter what approaches are used in assessing human capital, the amount spent on a person, his or her creative training potential, the profit to him or her in a variety of ways (not only in compliance with the current interest rate) and the benefit to him or her in his or her entire conscientious working life is an important factor. Consequently, the funds spent on a person are useful and effective in relation to all investments.

It is possible to imagine human capital in an empirical (quantitative) form, the international standard of Statistics - the Human Development Index (Human Potential Development Index - Isri) corresponds to the state local statistics on the professional education of the employed population, the level of life, the increase in incomes (see table). This made it possible to shed light on the legislative changes in the Republic of Uzbekistan in relation to other countries of the world in terms of human potential and to assess the state of human

potential taking into account professional education and its socio-economic Active results.

Conclusion and discussion.

2017-2019 century. during the analysis of the increase in ISR in Uzbekistan, on the one hand, the rapid increase in the education index (2017-2019 yy.on the other hand, the increase in gross domestic product (GDP) and the negative impact of the life expectancy index made it possible to determine the direction of the same growth of the ISR, which was conditioned by the increase in GDP (GDP) at 0,913 and reached 0,917). Entering into the group of moderately developed countries, the Republic of Uzbekistan was among the group of highly developed countries on the level of Education. This means that our country has an important human potential, which is necessary for its inclusion among the developed countries of the world.

2017-2019 century.growth of ISR in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Year	In Uzbekistan ISR *	ISR rating	In highly developed countries ISR	In moderately developed countries ISR
2019	0,72	106	0,957	0,691
2018	0,72	107	0,954	0,694
2017	0,71	108	0,953	0,695

Origin:Human development statistical update. 2017-2020 y.

CONCLUSION

As a result of a comparative analysis of the regional importance of the index of human development in the Republic of Uzbekistan, one can conclude that Isri has grown, but the growth process is relatively slow. The comparison of the index of countries is conditional, but it is very instructive for Uzbekistan.

In the direction of the growth of the Human Development Index, it is important to increase the level of retraining of the employed population with professional

knowledge, as well as the high level of development of the human capital of Uzbekistan. There is also a slow-moving direction.

Increasing the amount of investment in human capital is important for the formation of the "knowledge economy". Uzbekistan is equating to the level of world countries on the level of Education. However, the quality of knowledge of the population of the country often does not coincide with the time for the formation of a knowledge-based economy in the country.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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